

Before I Forget

Developed by: 3-Fold Games

Article contributed by: Brittany Westlund

Keywords

Cognitive Science, Dementia, Empathy, Gerontology, Identity, Mental Health, Psychology, Trauma

Figure 1. Screenshot from *Before I Forget* (2020). © 3-Fold Games. All rights remain with the creators.

Introduction

Before I Forget (see Figure 1) is a first-person 3D narrative game created by Chella Ramanan and Claire Morwood in 2020, developed and published through their micro-studio, 3-Fold Games. Players explore life as Sunita, a woman living with early-onset dementia. Developed in consultation with medical professionals and the UK-based charity Gaming the Mind, the game applies credible insights to deliver an authentic experience (3-Fold Games, n.d.; Wen, 2018). As players traverse Sunita's monochromatic home, household items trigger memories, coloring her surroundings and impacting her self-identity and perception of reality.

While not intended as a standalone educational resource, *Before I Forget* offers an intimate portrayal of the psychological and social effects of dementia through Sunita's memories and inner monologue. In higher education, the game complements formal curricula as an active learning exercise that provides insight into the lived experience of dementia. Moreover, *Before I Forget* encourages reflection and critical analysis, fosters empathy toward people living with dementia, and allows students to practice integrating emotional understanding with disciplinary expertise.

Facts

Release date:	2020
Developer:	3-Fold Games
Game type:	Digital
Number of players:	Singleplayer
Format:	Hybrid
Time frame:	Approximately 1 hour; designed for a single sitting
Languages:	Available in five languages on Steam, six on Xbox and Nintendo Switch
Environment:	Computer, Xbox One, or Nintendo Switch
Material:	N/A
Price:	USD \$7.99

Resonance & Criticism

Critics and players praise *Before I Forget* for its environmental storytelling, nuanced voice acting, and its focus on Sunita's individual experience. Reviewers often highlight that its short, hour-long playtime offers an impactful narrative that effectively conveys the effects of dementia on Sunita's memory, identity, and perception.

Before I Forget has a critic score of 88 on Metacritic and 82 on OpenCritic. Metacritic's audience score is 7.1, and it has a "Very Positive" rating on Steam. The game received early recognition at the XX+ Games Jam in Bristol, UK, in 2016, where it won the Audience Choice Award. It was nominated for 'Game Beyond Entertainment' at the BAFTA Games Awards (2020), the 'Off Broadway Award – Indie Game' by the New York Game Critics Circle (2020), and 'Most Innovative' at the Games for Change Awards (2021).

The game may not appeal to players expecting conventional game goals or structure; the experience is not about winning but about portraying an intimate story and simulating player experiences. Additionally, criticism has targeted its limited interactivity and fixed narrative, which reduces replay value.

Game Principle & Process

Before I Forget uses environmental storytelling and visual metaphors to convey the effects of dementia on memory, identity, and perception. The game reveals Sunita's memories and

emotional state through illustrated vignettes and voice-over. Photographs, documents, and notes spark memories that reveal Sunita's story and restore color to her desaturated home. Still, some areas remain grey, representing permanent memory gaps.

Sunita's foremost pursuit is to find her husband, Dylan. Her memories provide glimpses of their relationship, revealing the story in fragments. For example, Sunita finds an umbrella that prompts a scene of the couple caught in the rain. Later, a brochure reveals Dylan's music career, accompanied by a piano melody and an inner monologue. Each memory has a unique emotional impact on Sunita, which is represented both visually and through sound.

While continuing her search, Sunita loses her way, often wandering into dark closets. In other instances, she experiences visual distortions, reflecting common challenges associated with dementia. Eventually, Sunita finds a news article that brings devastating clarity to her world. The experience concludes once the player uncovers Sunita's full emotional arc.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

The main goal of *Before I Forget* is to examine the emotional impact of dementia from a first-person perspective. The creators aim to highlight the complexity of the condition, with Sunita reliving even happy memories throughout the game, dispelling tropes of "darkness and despair" associated with the condition (Wen, 2018).

Through Sunita's backstory and reflections, students can explore the complex relationship between memory, identity, and perception, recognizing how cognitive changes impact her emotional landscape. The game also invites students to reflect on how narrative and metaphor can convey individual experiences and to critically analyze the role of storytelling in fostering empathy and understanding.

The game's versatility makes it relevant across multiple disciplines. In higher education contexts such as psychology and cognitive science, health humanities, gerontology and aging studies, and narrative medicine, *Before I Forget* supports learning objectives by helping students make sense of abstract concepts through a patient's lived experience. Instructors can promote critical analysis by asking students to connect symptoms and in-game experiences to professional knowledge. The game encourages evaluating current strategies for educating students about dementia and exploring how storytelling could impact understanding and approach across various fields. Furthermore, the game inspires insights into care strategies, educational plans, and original projects that synthesize student learning. By engaging learners in these higher-order thinking skills, the game not only deepens subject knowledge but also cultivates empathy, critical reflection, and applied problem-solving.

Effectiveness

There are currently no empirical studies on the effectiveness of *Before I Forget* in educational settings. Instead, the game is most effective when used in active learning strategies that

combine gameplay with guided reflection. Instructors can integrate the game into lessons by pairing it with structured discussion questions, writing prompts, or creative assignments that allow students to process and articulate their experiences.

Drawing on dementia research and outreach, the game's narrative offers a clinically informed and ethically responsible portrayal that invites critical reflection on memory and identity. Sensory cues and visual metaphors make abstract symptoms more tangible, while the story's emotional impact can spark rich discussion beyond clinical case studies (Campbell, 2018). Additionally, students with no prior gaming experience can access and engage meaningfully with its content because the controls are simple and the hour-long playtime fits into a single class session.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

While *Before I Forget* offers a powerful, emotionally resonant portrayal of dementia, its strong emotional triggers may be complex for those personally affected by dementia (Campbell, 2018). The narrative arc is intense, particularly in the final scenes, which may be challenging for some audiences. The singular narrative also risks being interpreted as representative of all dementia experiences.

Some visual and navigational mechanics may pose challenges for players with disabilities. To move and interact with objects on a computer, players must rotate the mouse and click the left mouse button. Furthermore, the player must align objects with a centered reticle, which may present challenges for players with motor limitations. Since the game relies heavily on color and sound cues, players with color vision deficiency or hearing impairments may need supplemental descriptions or discussion to engage fully.

Importantly, the developers describe *Before I Forget* as an "impressionistic" experience rather than a formal educational tool (Wen, 2018). Instructors should supplement with factual information and context from trusted sources.

Reviewer(s): Johannes Katsarov

Sources

3-Fold Games. (n.d.). *Before I Forget* [Press factsheet].
<https://www.3foldgames.uk/press/before-i-forget/index.html>

3-Fold Games. (2020, July 16). *Before I Forget* [itch.io game page]. Itch.io.
<https://3foldgames.itch.io/before-i-forget>

- British Academy of Film and Television Arts. (n.d.). *Game beyond entertainment*.
<https://www.bafta.org/awards/games/game-beyond-entertainment>
- Campbell, K. (2018, August). The colours of memories [Interview with Chella Ramanan and Claire Morley]. *Possability Magazine*, 36–38.
https://issuu.com/2apublishing/docs/posmag_aug_2018/36
- Games for Change. (2021, June 3). *Announcing the 2021 G4C Awards finalists*.
https://www.gamesforchange.org/blog_posts/announcing-the-2021-g4c-awards-finalists-%F0%9F%8E%89/
- Metacritic. (n.d.). *Before I Forget* [Game reviews]. Retrieved August 14, 2025, from
<https://www.metacritic.com/game/before-i-forget/>
- New York Videogame Critics Circle. (2022, January 11). *Awards: All the awesome nominees, plus much more New York Game Awards info!*
<https://nygamecritics.com/2022/01/11/awards-all-the-awesome-nominees-plus-much-more-new-york-game-awards-info/>
- OpenCritic. (n.d.). *Before I Forget* [Game reviews]. Retrieved August 14, 2025, from
<https://opencritic.com/game/9828/before-i-forget>
- Wen, A. (2018, June 6). Before I Forget: The video game that tackles dementia. *The Guardian*.
<https://www.theguardian.com/games/2018/jun/06/before-i-forget-early-onset-dementia-video-game>